

Artificial Neural Networks and Response Surface Methodology Approach for Modelling Coated-Carbide Tools when Turning AISI-1045 Steel.

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation deals with the modelling and optimization of a three variable Face Centered Central Composite Design (FCCD) to study the combined effect of Cutting Speed, Feed Rate and the Side Cutting Edge Angle (SCEA) of the cutting edge on two response variables, Surface Roughness and Tangential Force. The experimental data was culled from the works of Noordin *et. al.*, (2004). The authors investigated the factors that influence the Surface Roughness and Tangential Force of a Multilayer Tungsten Carbide Tool when Turning AISI 1045 Steel. In this paper the comparison of the Surface Roughness and Tangential Force prediction models based on Response Surface Methodology (RSM) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) is described. The models were developed based on five-level design of experiments conducted on the performance of coated carbide tools when turning AISI 1045 steel. The RSM is mainly optimized by a multivariate quadratic model, and its prediction accuracy is also influenced by a non-fitting factor. ANN was one of the artificial intelligence techniques that explored complicated systems' relationships by fitting the existing data and back-propagating them using supervised learning. The ANN predictive models for Surface Roughness and Tangential Force were simulated using a Multi-Layer Feed-Forward Neural Network (MLFFN) architecture, and trained using Levenberg-Marquardt Backpropagation learning algorithm based on the generalized delta rule in the ratio of 70%: 15%: 15% for Training, Validation and Testing, respectively. The empirical model was fitted using nntool in statistics toolbox of MATLAB R2021. Mathematical models of second order RSM and developed ANN models were compared for surface roughness and Tangential Force using the Coefficient of Determination, R^2 and some selected error indices, namely, Mean Square Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD) and Spherical Probability Error (SPE). The results show that RSM models were larger than ANN models in terms of error indices, indicating that ANN model has higher predictive efficiency than the RSM models for Surface Roughness and Tangential Force. ANN predicted values lie closer to experimental values than the RSM predicted values in both responses. Thus, the comparison evidently indicates that the predictive capabilities of ANN models are far better than the RSM models and has significantly, a remarkable higher generalization capacity than the RSM models.

Keywords: Response Surface Methodology (RSM), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Multi-Layered Feed Forward Neural Network (MLFFNN), Back-Propagation algorithm (BP)

INTRODUCTION

Response surface methodology (RSM) is an empirical statistical modelling technique employed for multiple regression analyses using quantitative data obtained from properly designed experiments to solve multivariate equations simultaneously Rao *et.al.*, (2000).

Response surface methodology (RSM) is an important subject in the statistical design of experiments and is defined as a "collection of mathematical and statistical techniques useful for modeling and analysis of

problems in which a response of interest is influenced by several variables and the objective is to optimize the response". (Montgomery, 2013).

Response surface methodology was first discussed in the 1950s by Box and Wilson within chemical experimentation, and generally includes mathematical and statistical tools for both the design and analysis of response surfaces (Box & Wilson, 1951). Cornell A. J., (1990), defined Response surface method (RSM) as a set of techniques used in the empirical study of relationships. RSM is useful in three different situations (Myers & Montgomery, 2002): (i) statistical experimental design; in particular two or level factorial or fractional factorial design (ii) regression modeling techniques, and (iii) optimization method. The most common application of RSM is in Industrial, Biological and Clinical Science, Social Science, Food Science, and Physical and Engineering Sciences. The first goal of RSM is to find an optimum response, however, when there is more than one response then it is important to find the compromised optimum that does not optimizes the responses, (Oehlert, 2000). When there are constraints on the design data, then the experimental design has to meet requirements of the constraints. The second goal is to adjust the design variable in order to understand how the response changes in a given direction.

The basic theory of RSM is well established and is presented in a number of texts such as those by (Box & Draper, 1987; Box, Hunter & Hunter, 2005; Khuri, 2006 and Myers, Montgomery and Anderson-Cook, 2009). Though, Mead and Pike (1975) were the first to bring attention to the role of RSM to agriculture and biometric research in general. They also provided a survey of biological and agricultural journals that used response surface methods.

Myers and Montgomery (2002) presented an excellent literature on Response surface methodology and can be referred to for more details on RSM analysis. In brief, 2^k factorial design is often used to fit linear and non-linear (second order) response surface models for k number of input variables. These set of input variables are also termed as natural variables as they are given in their respective units. In RSM, natural variables ($x_1, x_2, x_3 \dots x_k$) are converted into coded variables using the following relationship;

$$\xi_1 = \frac{x_i - [\max(x_i) + \min(x_i)]/2}{[\max(x_i) - \min(x_i)]/2} \tag{1.1}$$

The range of variation in the input parameters x represents the maximum and minimum values. The combination of input parameters (sample points) determines the output response (y) by performing regression analysis based on least square error approach to fit a linear or nonlinear regression model. The output response corresponding to each combination of input parameters can be obtained either from the established functional relationship between input and output or through numerical analysis. Verification of the model adequacy of the fitted model is required to ensure that none of the least square assumptions are violated, and, that the model provides an adequate approximation of the true system. RSM has been applied in various experimental designs involving extraction process (Huang et al. 2008), food preservation (Ölmez & Akbas, 2009; Rico et al. 2008), fermentation (Dhandhukia and Thakkar, 2008) as well as other discipline of engineering. (Yang, 2008; Montgomery, 2013), defined RSM as a sequential procedure plan that recommends beginning the design from the assumption of first-order linear model with interaction and springing to the second-order full polynomial model with interaction, this occurs when there is a significant curvature. The above procedure gives us a polynomial model that has main effects and interactions effects that is suitable to express a response surface when analysis of the result reveals no evidence of pure quadratic curvature in the response of interest, on the hand, if there exists a curvature as enumerated earlier, the process Behavior will then require a quadratic model.

Response surface methodology is useful for factorial experiments with k quantitative factors that are undertaken so as to determine the combination of levels of factors at which each of the quantitative factors must be set in order to optimize the response in some sense. Let there be k independent variables denoted by x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k and the response variable be y and N the number of observations. The response as a function of input factors is represented as

$$y_m = f(x_{1m}, x_{2m}, \dots, x_{km}) + e_m \quad (1.2)$$

where $m=1,2,\dots, N$ represents the N observations and x_{jm} is the level of the j^{th} factor in the m^{th} treatment combination, $j=1,2,\dots, k$; $m=1,2,\dots, N$, and y_m denote the response obtained from the m^{th} treatment combination. The function f describes the form in which the response and the input variables are related and e_m is the random error associated with the m^{th} observation. In practice, the mathematical form of f is not known; we, therefore, often approximate it, within the experimental region, by a polynomial of suitable degree in variables, x_{jm} . The adequacy of the fitted polynomial is tested through the usual analysis of variance.

Besides RSM, Artificial Neural Network (ANN) has also been broadly researched to optimize process because of its effective, robust, and prominent features in capturing the nonlinear relationships between parameters and response in a complex system. There is a growing concern among researchers around the globe in the employment of RSM and ANN as tools for prediction and optimization. A Neural Network is a combination of different features that evaluate the various input features and defines pattern in the data using Neural Network architecture. Artificial Neural Networks are one of the deep learning algorithms that simulate the workings of neurons in the human brain. Neural Network, put simply, is a calculation which is more of biological nervous system. Mathematically, it is a set of linear algebra calculation that maps the input x to output layer y with the help of activation function. Guoqiang (2000) defined An Artificial Neural Network as system whose neurons are interconnected, he reiterated that every unit in ANN has info, yield qualities and actualizes nearby algorithms AIQadi *et al*, (2020), defined ANN as a computational mathematical model that contains a set of fully connected neurons which are arranged in two or more layers. Bandy H. (1997), pointed out that, Artificial neural networks are information processing structures providing the (often unknown) connection between input and output data. José Morales and José Huanca, (2020), reiterated that, Artificial Neural Networks are connectionist systems formed by numerous process units called neurons connected to each other, which adapt their structure through learning techniques to solve problems of function approximation and pattern classification. According to Hindi *et al*, (2020), two operations are implemented by each neuron (i) calculating the sum product and the attendant weights (ii) calculate the neuron output with respect to the selected activation function. However, Ngata et al (2003), puts it that, the ANN model is potentially more accurate when all the experimental data are included in the network architecture, Artificial Neural Networks are used for solving a variety of problems, such as finance, manufacturing, electronic, medical etc., Hagan et al (1996), Negarestani *et al.*, (2002), reiterated that, generally speaking, an ANN consists of an input and an output layer and can also contain hidden layers, and that Networks with no hidden layer are only able to perform linear tasks. Similarly, M.Y. Rafiq *et al*, (2001), in the same vein, pointed out that a second hidden layer is only necessary for discontinuous problems. I. A. Basheer and M. Hajmeer, (2000), pointed out that ANN consists of a number of nodes that represent the computing units (or neurons), connections (axons and dendrites) between those nodes, connection weights (synapses) and thresholds (activity in the soma), he reiterated that, a non-linear transfer function, often a sigmoidal function, is applied to the weighted sums of each neuron. and that, Networks with no hidden layer are only able to perform linear tasks, while M.Y. Rafiq *et al*, (2001), in the same vein, pointed out that a second hidden layer is only necessary for discontinuous problems. According to Silva et al (2016), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) have been around for a while, but the research potential is still huge, he, however, pointed out that, ANNs have been used successfully in both classification and regression problems. Ahangar *et al.*, (2010) made use of neural network regression for stock price prediction. Moreover, they suggested that there is an increasing interest in ANNs for problems related to forecasting. Daniel Graupe, (2007), opined that ANN modelling can be an excellent approach in simulating output results. Pirdashti M, *et al*, reviewed a variety of ANN applications in chemical engineering that dealt with critical aspect of ANN topology, modelling strategy, the methods of developing and training the data. Erenturk and Erenturk, (2006) compared the use of genetic algorithm and ANN approaches to study the drying of carrots. They demonstrated that the

proposed neural network model not only minimized the R^2 of the predicted results but also removed the predictive dependency on the mathematical models. Goyal and Goyal tested the ANN with a single hidden layer consisting of 3–20 neuron. Based on the studies, they concluded that the number of nodes in the hidden layer should be correlated with the amount of input data.

ANNs are artificial adaptive systems that are inspired by the functioning processes of the human brain, it is an advancement in the field of Deep Learning that is based on the biological neural network, such as the brain. The basic unit of the brain is known as a neuron. There are approximately 86 billion neurons in the nervous system which are connected to between 10^{14} - 10^{15} synapses, and transmits information through electro-chemical signals. The biological **neuron** is composed of multiple **dendrites**, a **nucleus**, an **axon** and **synapses**, as can be seen in the figure 1 below.

Figure 1: The given figure illustrates the typical diagram of Biological Neural Network.

ANNs try to mimic the working principles of the Biological Neural Networks (BNNs). The diagram above is drawn to give a brief explanation on the comparative study of how this concept of BNN is extended further to design an ANN. Basically, the basic functional units of the neural system in the brain is to generate electrical signals which are called action potential which allows them to quickly transmit information over long distances. So, almost all the neurons have three functions, first, they receive signals from the environment, and then process those incoming signals and also determine whether the information will pass along the neurons or not, the third task is to communicate those signals to the target cells. The Dendrites are responsible for receiving the incoming signals from the environment, and the functionality of the Cell Nucleus also known as Soma is responsible for processing the input signals and also decides whether that neuron should fire the outputs or not. So, whether information should be propagated or not further to next neuron will be decided by the Cell Nucleus. The utility of the Axon is getting processed signal from Soma, and then transfer the processed information to the Synapse. So, incoming signals are of two types; the Excitatory Signals and the Inhibitory Signals. The Excitatory Signals are the electrical impulses that gets the Dendrites excited or activated, hence making it to propagate information further to the next neuron, however, the second category is the Inhibitory Signals which means that they keep the neurons away from firing. On the other hand, the artificial neurons that mimic this architecture are called perceptron. The ANN is comprised of three layers, the input layer, the hidden layer and the output layer, and these layers linked together with their attendant weights which are arbitrarily chosen according to the contribution or importance of the input variable, these processes are called the Network Architecture. The structure of the ANN architecture can be a single layer architecture also known as Single-Layer Perceptron (SLP) or a multiple layer architecture also known as Multi-Layer

Perceptron (MLP). This research work was carried using the Feed-Forward Neural Network Multilayered Perceptron (FFNNMLP) with Backpropagation algorithm. Figures 2 below is an ANN with (3:10:2) architectures.

Figure 2: The given figure illustrates the typical diagram of the Artificial Neural Network with one hidden layer for the case study

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The case study is a three variable Face Centered Central Composite Design (FCCD) experimental data obtained from the works of (Noordin *et al.*, 2004), titled ‘Application of Response Surface Methodology in Describing the Performance of Coated-Carbide Tools when Turning AISI 1045 Steel’. The design has sixteen distinct design points including two replicates at the central point. The secondary data extracted was used to explore the region for fitting the first and second order models. The effects of the process parameters such as Cutting Speed, Feed Rate and the Side Cutting Edge Angle (SCEA) on Surface Roughness and Tangential Force were investigated using five level Face Centered Central Composite Design. The three variable Face Centered Central Composite Designed experimental data with process parameters were $X_1 = \text{Cutting Speed (m/min)}$, $X_2 = \text{Feed (mm/rev)}$ and $X_3 = \text{SCEA (}^\circ\text{)}$. The response variables were a function of the three variable inputs, X_1 , X_2 and X_3 as shown in equation (3.1)

$$y_i = f(x_1, x_2 \text{ and } x_3) + \varepsilon \quad (3.1)$$

In this study, the relationship between the three operating variables and the responses was established using the full quadratic model. The same data was used to train the Artificial Neural Network

Multilayer Feed-Forward Neural Network

A Multilayered Feed-Forward ANN with error Back-Propagation (BP) was employed using MATLAB R2021 (MathWorks Inc., USA), a strict learning scheme is of utmost significance for proper training of the network to assure useful mapping between inputs and outputs resulting in constant improvement of the network with effective error reduction, Beale *et al.*, (2010), Witek *et.al.*, (2014). A Feed-Forward network with back-propagation is most commonly used in process optimization to minimize error at each iteration, Turan *et.al.*, (2011).

The model considered in this research is the Multilayered Feed-Forward Neural Network (MLFNN) which included two output variables and three input variables. The topology shown in Fig. 2 is a network having one hidden layer (with a logsigmoid activation function) and two output layers (linear function). The network is a (3-10-2)- MLP topology; that is, an ANN architecture having 3 input variables, 10 neurons and 2 output variables. The neurons in the hidden layer significantly affect accuracy and prediction of the optimal conditions. If the network topology is simple, the trained networks cannot learn properly. Therefore, neurons were optimized to determine optimum neuron using the best predictive capability and accuracy of the model. In general, the value at the predicted output unit y_k as in Equation (3.8) is always a function of the inputs, the synaptic weights, the bias values and the activation function. The proposed RSM and ANN effectiveness were evaluated based on the error indices as shown in equations (3.4) – (3.6). The prevailing regions of exploration were 240(N) – 375(N) of Cutting Speed, 0.18(mm/rev) – 0.28(mm/rev) of Feed Rate and -5(°) – 0 (°) of SCEA. The same designs were utilized to train a Feed-forward Multi-layered Perceptron (MLP) Artificial Neural Network (ANN) with Backpropagation Algorithm. The objective was to determine and compare the predictive capabilities and accuracies of Response Surface Model and Artificial Neural Networks. The proposed effectiveness of the two methodologies were compared based on coefficient of determination (R^2), and some selected error parameters, namely, Mean Square Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD) and Spherical Probability Error (SPE), (Akilu et al., 2021) and (Sarve et al., 2015), as given in equations (3.3) – (3.6), respectively. The calculation is shown as the following equations:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_{Acti} - y_{Predi})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_{Acti} - \bar{y})^2} \quad (3.3)$$

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_{Acti} - y_{Predi})^2 \quad (3.4)$$

$$MAD(\%) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{|y_{Acti} - \bar{y}_{Predi}|}{|y_{Acti}|} \times 100 \quad (3.5)$$

$$SPE = \frac{RMSE}{\bar{y}_{Acti}} \quad (3.6)$$

where N is the number experimental runs, y_{act} is the actual response, y_{pred} is the predicted response, \bar{y}_{act} is the average actual response and \bar{y}_{pred} is the average predicted response.

Data Presentation

This study investigated the factors that influence the surface roughness and tangential force of a multilayer tungsten carbide tool when turning AISI 1045 steel. The factors so investigated were the Cutting Speed, Feed Rate, and the Side Cutting Edge Angle (SCEA) of the cutting edge. The experiments were based on a face-centered central composite design (FCD). The factors and levels used in the experiment were shown in Table 1 of the paper and are reproduced in coded and natural variables as Table 1.

Table 1: Experimental data in coded and natural variables based on FCCD

X1	X2	X3	Cutting Speed (N)	Feed Rate(mm/rev)	SCEA (N)	Surface Roughness (μ)	Tangential Force (N)
-1	-1	-1	240	0.18	-5	1.68	559.22
1	-1	-1	375	0.18	-5	1.4	432.27
-1	1	-1	240	0.28	-5	3.18	436.1
1	1	-1	375	0.28	-5	2.95	351.14
-1	-1	1	240	0.18	0	1.2	366.48
1	-1	1	375	0.18	0	1.42	440.92
-1	1	1	240	0.28	0	3.8	428.88
1	1	1	375	0.28	0	3.25	525.85
-1	0	0	240	0.23	-2.5	2.14	372.24
1	0	0	375	0.23	-2.5	2.08	372.83
0	-1	0	307.5	0.18	-2.5	1.14	550.14
0	1	0	307.5	0.28	-2.5	2.99	553.5
0	0	-1	307.5	0.23	-5	2.17	465.4
0	0	1	307.5	0.23	0	2.32	540.77
0	0	0	307.5	0.23	-2.5	1.76	443.1
0	0	0	307.5	0.23	-2.5	1.74	395.98

Model Specification

Response Surface Model

The Second-Order Response Surface Model is defined as:

$$y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i x_i + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{ii} x_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{j=1+1}^k \beta_{ij} x_i x_j + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (3.7)$$

where $\beta_0, \beta_i, \beta_{ii}$ and β_{ij} are the constant, the linear, the quadratic and the interaction terms, respectively, x_i, x_j are the coded independent variables ε_m is the uncorrelated random error component in the observation with a mean zero and a constant variance σ^2

Artificial Neural Networks Model

The ANN Architecture was trained using the Muti-layered Feed-Forward Neural Network with Back-Propagation Algorithm with a Sigmoid Activation Function

Sigmoid Activation Function

The Sigmoid Activation Function and its derivative are given by

$$\varphi(\theta) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\theta)}$$

and

$$\varphi'(\theta) = \varphi(\theta)[1 - \varphi(\theta)]$$

respectively

Feed-Forward Neural Network (FFNN)

The general expression for a Feed-Forward Neural Network (FFNN) operation can be summarized as:

$$y_k = f(y_{inK}) = f\left(w_{ok} + \sum_{j=1}^p f\left(v_{0j} + \sum_{i=1}^n x_i v_{ij}\right)w_{jk}\right) \quad (3.8)$$

where

y_k is the activation function applied to the net input y_{inK}

y_{inK} is the net input of the k th output neuron to the final output

w_{ok} are the bias values connecting the k th output neuron

v_{0j} are the bias values connecting the j th output neuron

x_i is the input signal ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$)

v_{ij} is the synaptic weight associated with the i th input to the j th neuron

w_{jk} is the synaptic weight associated with the j th input to the k th neuron

Back-Propagation Algorithm

The general Back-Propagation Algorithm can be derived iteratively using the following steps:

$$\Delta w = \eta \delta_j O_i$$

If j is an input unit

$$\delta_j = O_j(1 - O_j)(t_j - O_j)$$

If j is a hidden unit

$$\delta_j = O_j(1 - O_j) \sum_k \delta_k w_{kj}$$

where

η is a constant called the learning rate

t_j is the target output

δ_j is the error measure for unit j

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis are presented in Tables 2-7 and Figures 3-8

All calculations were done using two advanced statistical software packages namely, Design-Expert version 13 (Trial Version) and MATLAB R2021. Both packages were utilized for the analysis of the Central Composite Designed experimental data used in this research work. The Design Expert was used for the analysis of the RSM, and a multilayered Feed-Forward ANN with error backpropagation (BP) was analyzed using the Statistical Toolbox, Neural Network tool in MATLAB R2021.

Table 2: ANOVA for Full Quadratic model for Surface Roughness

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	Remarks
Model	9.71	9	1.08	35.88	0.0002	significant
A-Cutting Speed	0.0810	1	0.0810	2.69	0.1518	
B-Feed	8.70	1	8.70	289.50	< 0.0001	
C-SCEA	0.0372	1	0.0372	1.24	0.3085	
AB	0.0648	1	0.0648	2.16	0.1925	
AC	0.0041	1	0.0041	0.1347	0.7262	
BC	0.2381	1	0.2381	7.92	0.0306	
A ²	0.0434	1	0.0434	1.44	0.2750	
B ²	0.0183	1	0.0183	0.6080	0.4652	
C ²	0.1827	1	0.1827	6.08	0.0488	
Residual	0.1804	6	0.0301			
Lack of Fit	0.1802	5	0.0360	180.21	0.0565	not significant
Pure Error	0.0002	1	0.0002			
Cor Total	9.89	15				
R²						0.9818
Adjusted R²						0.9544
Predicted R²						0.7565

Table 3: ANOVA for Full Quadratic model for Tangential Force

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	Remarks
Model	69858.73	9	7762.08	4.79	0.0350	significant
A-Cutting Speed	159.28	1	159.28	0.0984	0.7644	
B-Feed	286.87	1	286.87	0.1771	0.6885	
C-SCEA	345.39	1	345.39	0.2133	0.6605	
AB	520.35	1	520.35	0.3213	0.5914	
AC	18366.78	1	18366.78	11.34	0.0151	
BC	15451.06	1	15451.06	9.54	0.0214	
A ²	30362.49	1	30362.49	18.75	0.0049	
B ²	13655.00	1	13655.00	8.43	0.0272	
C ²	1423.11	1	1423.11	0.8787	0.3847	
Residual	9716.90	6	1619.48			
Lack of Fit	8606.75	5	1721.35	1.55	0.5416	not significant
Pure Error	1110.15	1	1110.15			
Cor Total	79575.63	15				
R²						0.8779
Adjusted R²						0.6947
Predicted R²						0.4098

Figure 3: Predicted Vs Actual Plot for Surface Roughness

Figure 4: Predicted Vs Actual Plot for Tangential Force

Figure 5: Performance Evaluation Tool for Surface Roughness

Figure 6: Correlation Coefficient (R) Fit Performance Distribution Plots for Surface Roughness

Figure 7: Validation Performance Graph for Surface Roughness

Figure 8: Performance Evaluation Tool for Tangential Force

Neural Network

The diagram shows a feedforward neural network. It starts with an **Input** layer of 3 nodes. These connect to a **Hidden Layer** of 10 nodes. Each hidden node receives weights (W) and bias (b), which are summed (+) and passed through an activation function. The hidden layer connects to an **Output Layer** of 1 node, which also receives weights (W) and bias (b), is summed (+), and passes through an activation function. Finally, the output layer connects to a single **Output** node.

Algorithms

Data Division: Random (dividerand)
 Training: Levenberg-Marquardt (trainlm)
 Performance: Mean Squared Error (mse)
 Calculations: MEX

Progress

Epoch:	0	9 iterations	1000
Time:		0:00:00	
Performance:	1.63	2.81e-06	0.00
Gradient:	1.15	0.00299	1.00e-07
Mu:	0.00100	1.00e-06	1.00e+10
Validation Checks:	0	6	6

Plots

(plotperform)
 (plottrainstate)
 (plotregression)

Plot Interval: 1 epochs

✔ **Opening Performance Plot**

Figure 9: Correlation Coefficient (R) Fit Performance Distribution Plots for Tangential Force

Figure 10: Validation Performance Graph for Tangential force

Table 4: Validation Data Set for Experimentally Determined ANN and RSM Predicted Values of Surface Roughness

Run	Actual Value	RSM Predicted Value	RSM Residual	ANN Predicted Value	ANN Residual
1	1.68	1.58	0.0997	1.6801	-1E-04
2	1.4	1.54	-0.1353	1.4	0
3	3.18	3.28	-0.1013	3.3145	-0.1345
4	2.95	2.88	0.0737	2.9253	0.0247
5	1.2	1.31	-0.1123	1.2	0
6	1.42	1.36	0.0627	1.42	0
7	3.8	3.7	0.0967	3.7997	0.0003
8	3.25	3.39	-0.1383	3.2122	0.0378
9	2.14	2.12	0.0172	2.1401	-1E-04
10	2.08	1.94	0.1372	2.087	-0.007
11	1.14	1.05	0.0852	1.1406	-0.0006
12	2.99	2.92	0.0692	2.99	0
13	2.17	2.11	0.0632	2.17	0
14	2.32	2.23	0.0912	2.32	0
15	1.76	1.9	-0.1445	1.75	0.01
16	1.74	1.9	-0.1645	1.75	-0.01

Table 5: Validation Data Set for Experimentally Determined ANN and RSM Predicted Values of Tangential Force

Run	Actual Value	RSM Predicted Value	RSM Residual	ANN Predicted Value	ANN Residual
1	559.22	551.03	8.19	559.2198	0.0002
2	432.27	431.09	1.18	433.6237	-1.3537
3	436.1	436.29	-0.1939	436.5153	-0.4153
4	351.14	348.61	2.53	351.144	-0.004
5	366.48	379.06	-12.58	366.5672	-0.0872
6	440.92	450.78	-9.86	460.8016	-19.8816
7	428.88	440.11	-11.23	428.9011	-0.0211
8	525.85	544.09	-18.24	525.825	0.025
9	372.24	356.42	15.82	372.3924	-0.1524
10	372.83	348.44	24.39	373.014	-0.184
11	550.14	537.07	13.07	550.1369	0.0031
12	553.5	526.36	27.14	553.5085	-0.0085
13	465.4	477.1	-11.7	466.4664	-1.0664
14	540.77	488.86	51.91	515.7474	25.0226
15	443.1	459.75	-16.65	454.6267	-11.5267
16	395.98	459.75	-63.77	559.2198	0.0002

Figure 11: Actual versus RSM and ANN predicted values for Surface Roughness

Figure 12: Actual versus RSM and ANN predicted values for Tangential Force

Table 6: Comparative Fit Analysis of RSM and ANN Models for Surface Roughness

Fit Parameter		Model	
		RSM	ANN
Determination Coefficients	R^2	0.9818	0.9979
Mean Square Error	MSE	1.13E-02	1.27E-03
Mean Absolute Deviation	MAD (%)	3.55E-05	1.41E-02
Spherical Probability Error	SPE	4.82E-02	1.01E-03

Table 7: Comparative Fit Analysis of RSM and ANN Models for Tangential Force

Fit Parameter		Model	
		RSM	ANN
Determination Coefficients	R^2	0.8779	0.9422
Mean Square Error	MSE	607.32	287.31
Mean Absolute Deviation	MAD (%)	8.43E-05	5.90E-04
Spherical Probability Error	SPE	5.45E-02	3.75E-02

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The main purpose of experimental designs is to take into account the factors that are considered likely to have an effect on the response variable, and consequently minimize the experimental error. In this work, experimental design of Coated-Carbide Tools when Turning AISI-1045 Steel was carried out to minimize the Surface Roughness and maximize Tangential Force using RSM. The RSM and the ANN networks were trained using CCD experimental data in Table 1. The accuracies of the models were determined using the full quadratic model

RSM Modeling

The RSM based models are structured in nature and are useful for obtaining sensitivity analysis and relationship between different input and output components when they are present in a limited number, Bezerra *et.al* (2008). The experimental values for all responses (independent variables) under different conditions are presented in Table 1 in coded and natural forms. The independent variables (inputs) and dependent variables (responses) were fitted to the second order polynomial function and examined for the goodness of fit. The coefficient of determination (R^2) which is defined as the ratio of explained variation to the total variation; a measure of the degree of fit was calculated to check the adequacy and fitness of the model. The value of R^2 was calculated to be 0.9818 for Surface Roughness which implies that 2% of the variability in the data was not explained by the model. The Error Parameter values associated with Surface Roughness were, 1.13E-02, 3.55E-05 and 4.82E-02 for Mean Square Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD) and Spherical Probability Error (SPE), respectively.

For Tangential Force, the value of R^2 was calculated to be 0.8779 implying that 88% of the variability in the data was explained by the model. The calculated Error Parameter values were 607.32, 8.43E-05 and 5.45E-02 for Mean Square Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD) and Spherical Probability Error (SPE), respectively.

ANN Modeling

ANN-based process model was developed using the most popular Feed-Forward ANN architecture namely, Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) with Back-Propagation Algorithm. The Back-Propagation Algorithm allows modification of the connection weight and biases to achieve minimum error function by using the Gradient Descent Method (GDM). The sigmoidal function was applied to the neurons of the hidden layer as well as the output layer. The first step of ANN modeling was to optimize a neural network with the aim of obtaining an ANN model with a minimal dimension and minimal errors in training and testing. The designed experiment and their respective experimental yields were used to train the network. The network is an MLP consisting of three layers, namely, the input layer (independent variables), the hidden layer and the output layer (dependent variables), classified as a (3, 10, 2) architecture. To avoid over-training and over-parameterization, the network was configured by partitioning the experimental data during training, and was calibrated and trained with a supervised learning technique using FFNN with Levenberg-Marquardt Backpropagation algorithm in the ratio of 70%: 15%: 15% for Training, Validation and Testing, respectively. A-(3, 10, 2) architecture is an MLP network structure that comprised an input layer (dependent variables) consisting of 3 neurons, a hidden layer consisting of 10 neurons, and an output layer (independent variables) consisting of 2 neurons with a learning rate of 0.75, (Figure 2). The inputs chosen in this study are Cutting Speed, Feed Rate and Side Cutting Edge Angle (SCEA) while the outputs are Surface Roughness and Tangential Force. The training process was run by trial-and-error search method until a minimum of Mean Square Error (MSE) was reached in the validation process and the performance of trained network was estimated based on the accuracy of the neural network to produce outputs that are equal or near to target (predicted) values. The performance of the Artificial Neural is verified by the evaluated error parameters, namely, Correlation Coefficient (R), Mean Square Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD) and Spherical Probability Error (SPE), Equations (3.3) – (3.6). Figures 5 and 8 and Figures 7 and 10 are performance evaluation tools and Validation Performance Graph for Surface Roughness and Tangential Force, respectively. The first section from the training window gives information about the number of input features, number of neurons in the hidden layer and number of output features in the Neural Network. The second section displays the default algorithm parameters, and the third section provides progress of the Neural Network. The validation performance graph

provides information of performance of training, validation and testing data. The performance is said to be good if the graph follows three points, (i) cross-entropy is less (ii) the test and validation error are both comparable (iii) the graph indicates where the best validation occurs. By looking into the progress, it can be concluded that, for Surface Roughness, the training stopped when the validation error increased for fifth iteration which occurred at epoch 5 with best validation performance of 1.2363 while for Tangential Force, the training stopped when the validation error increased for sixth iteration which occurred at epoch 9 with best validation performance of 0.0131.

Figure 6 shows the experimental versus the computed ANN data's spread plot in both training, testing and validation network for Surface Roughness. The correlation coefficients (R) values for training (0.99998), validation (1), testing (1) and all prediction sets (0.99903), and all prediction sets (0.98386). Figure 9 shows the experimental versus the computed ANN data's spread plot in both training, testing and validation network for Tangential Force. The correlation coefficients (R) values for training (1), validation (1), testing (1) and all prediction sets (0.9723). Nearly each data point in both responses has been scattered around the 45° line indicating excellent compatibility between the experimental and predicted output data values by ANN.

Table 4 shows the best combination of the ANN parameters to predict the output parameter (Surface Roughness) most accurately. The values of R^2 , MSE, MAD and SPE obtained from the ANNs were 0.9979, 1.27E-03, 1.41E-02 and 1.01E-03, respectively.

Similarly, Table 5 shows the best combination of the ANN parameters to predict the output parameter (Tangential Force) most accurately. The values of R^2 , MSE, MAD and SPE obtained from the ANNs were 0.9422, 287.31, 5.90E-04 and 3.75E-02, respectively.

Comparative evaluation of ANN and RSM Models

In order to evaluate the goodness of fit and predictive capabilities of the RSM and ANN constructed models for Surface Roughness and Tangential Force, some selected error parameters, namely, Determination coefficients R^2 , the Mean Square Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD) and Spherical Probability Error (SPE) and were carried out between experimental and predicted data. Table 6 shows the predictive indices for RSM and ANN for Surface Roughness. The values were calculated based on Table 4 and Equations (3.3) – (3.6) The RSM values for (R^2), MSE, MAD and SPE were 0.9818, 1.13E-02 3.55E-05 and 4.82E-02, respectively, and the ANN values for (R^2), MSE, MAD and SPE were 0.9979, 1.27E-03, 1.41E-02 and 1.01E-03, respectively.

Similarly, Table 7 also shows the predictive indices for RSM and ANN for Tangential Force. The values were calculated based on Table 5 and Equations (3.3) – (3.6) The RSM values for (R^2), MSE, MAD and SPE were 0.8779, 607, 8.43E-05 and 5.45E-02, respectively, and the ANN values for (R^2), MSE, MAD and SPE were 0.9422, 287.31, 5.90E-04 and 3.75E-02, respectively.

To study the modeling abilities of the RSM and ANN models, the values predicted by the RSM and ANN models were plotted against the corresponding experimental values while the overall performance of the models was determined in terms of capability and accuracy in predictions. Figures 11 and 12 depict the experimental values and predicted values of RSM and ANN. The closer the value of R^2 to the unity, the better the empirical model fits the actual data validate the accuracy of the model. It is usually necessary to check the fitted model to ensure it provides an adequate approximation to the real system. Closeness of the predicted values to the experimental values validates the accuracy of the model. The higher the values of R^2 and the lower the values of the error qualifiers, the better the goodness of fit. It can be seen that both figures indicated that the data points of ANN responses showed no overfitting and the model is statistically more suitable when compared to RSM responses. However, as indicated, the ANN predicted values are much closer to the experimentally measured data, suggesting that the ANN model has superior prediction ability than the RSM model. The closer the value of R^2 to the unity, the better the empirical model fits the actual data. It is usually necessary to check the fitted model to ensure it provides an adequate approximation to the real system.

CONCLUSION

This paper aimed to evaluate and compare the Response Surface and Artificial Neural Network models. Based on the comparative analysis of the values of the error parameter indices of the RSM and ANN models for Surface Roughness and Tangential Force for validated data sets, the ANN model has demonstrated superior virtues in terms of robustness, accuracy and efficiency than the RSM model both in data fitting and prediction capabilities. The lines of predicted values of overall desirability using the MLR model and the ANN model had a similar flow. However, a better fit was noted for the ANN model. Though, it appears possible to use both models, never the less, the ANN model is a more reliable and accurate tool for predicting the overall desirability of Surface Roughness and Tangential Force

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